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INDIGOFERA TINCTORIA: HISTORY, BOTANY AND ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE FOR UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the plant Indigofera tinctoria L., its history, botanical characteristics and economic significance for Uzbekistan. The use of this plant in the textile industry as a source of natural blue dye, as well as its agronomic properties, including the ability to enrich the soil with nitrogen and high nutritional value for livestock, are considered. The importance of studying the bioecological features and methods of growing indigo for increasing its productivity and sustainability in the conditions of Uzbekistan is emphasized. The article also focuses on the need for scientific research aimed at optimizing the conditions of cultivation and integrating indigo into sustainable agriculture systems.*

Keywords: *Indigofera tinctoria, natural dyes, textile industry, bioecological features, soil fertility, propagation methods*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается использование этого растения в текстильной промышленности как источника натурального синего красителя, а также его агрономические свойства, включая способность обогащать почву азотом и высокую питательную ценность для животноводства. Подчеркивается важность изучения биоэкологических особенностей и методов выращивания индигоферы для повышения ее урожайности и устойчивости в условиях Узбекистана. Статья также акцентирует внимание на необходимости научных исследований, направленных на оптимизацию условий культивирования и интеграцию индигоферы в системы устойчивого сельского хозяйства.*

Ключевые слова. *Indigofera tinctoria, текстильная промышленность, биоэкологические особенности, плодородие почвы, агротехнология возделывания.*

INTRODUCTION. For centuries, people have been engaged in dyeing fabrics in the textile industry. This process was of great importance for creating beautiful and unique fabrics that reflected the culture and traditions of various peoples. In the mid-19th century, before the advent of affordable and easy-to-use bright dyes, aniline dyes were primarily used. These dyes were popular for their durability and color intensity. However, with the emergence of concerns about the impact of chemicals on the environment, the scientific community began actively seeking alternatives.

Analysis of scientific sources shows that interest in natural dyes derived from plants is growing every year. For four thousand years before our era, the Egyptians collected information about types of colorful plants and their significance. They found inscriptions with images of plants on papyrus and clay tablets used in ancient Egypt. These findings indicate that the Egyptians not only used plants to dye fabrics, but also delved into their chemical composition, developing special techniques.

It is known that the Egyptian Queen Cleopatra, known for her refined taste and desire for beauty, ordered the sails of her ships to be painted blue. This was not only a symbol of luxury and power, but also an indicator of the use of natural dyes in the upper classes. In addition, the discovery of fabrics dyed in red indicates that the Egyptians had significant knowledge in the field of textile production and dyes. Such discoveries allow us to understand how ancient civilizations valued and used natural resources to create beautiful and durable materials.

Natural vivid colors are mainly obtained from plants. A special place in this regard is occupied by the plant *Indigofera tinctoria* L. This wonderful plant has long been widely used in various fields. In the textile industry, its blue pigment is used for dyeing fabrics, creating beautiful and durable shades. In agriculture, it also plays an important role, contributing to increased soil fertility and enriching it with nitrogen, which has a beneficial effect on the growth of melons, fruit trees, tea and coffee plantations, and vineyards [1,4].

BOTANICAL DESCRIPTION. *Indigofera tinctoria* is a tropical annual herbaceous plant belonging to the legume (Fabaceae) family. The roots have a yellowish or brownish hue and penetrate to a depth of 0.3 to 0.4 meters. A single plant can have 40 to 80 root nodules, with an average size ranging from 0.7 to 1.0 centimeters. The plant reaches a height of 1.0 to 1.5 meters. The stem is light green in color and covered with fine hairs. The leaves are arranged alternately on the stem and consist of both simple and compound leaves with a semi-oval shape. The compound leaves are imparipinnate, with 3-5 leaflets in the lower part of the stem and 5-9 leaflets in the middle part. The calyx has a bell-shaped form and is bisexual. The reddish-yellow flowers have a curved (zygomorphic) shape and are generally arranged in groups in the leaf axils. The inflorescences form a head.

The fruit is a dry brown pod 0.5 to 1.2 cm in length. As the fruits mature, the seed color transforms from green to bright red, while the pods become deep brown. Each pod contains an average of 2 to 4 seeds, and an inflorescence forms an average of 6 to 72 seeds. The weight of 1,000 seeds is 10-12 grams. After the pod ripening process is complete, the leaves begin to yellow and drop.

Obtaining a high-quality crop of plants requires a deep understanding of their biological characteristics and reaction to environmental influences. One of the promising representatives of medicinal and dye plants is the indigo plant (*Indigofera tinctoria* L.), which belongs to the legume family. This plant has ancient roots and has significant potential in various fields of application [10].

ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE. Despite the long history of *Indigofera* cultivation, its bioecological characteristics and cultivation methods remain insufficiently studied. To achieve optimal results in growing this plant, it is necessary to take into account many factors, ranging from soil composition and light levels to irrigation frequency and temperature conditions [5,7].

Given the biological characteristics of *Indigofera tinctoria* and its belonging to the legume family, the plant has high potential for use in the agricultural conditions of Uzbekistan. Symbiotic nitrogen fixation plays a key role in providing the plant with the necessary nutrients for its growth and development. It should be noted that *Indigofera tinctorial* has a unique ability to adapt to arid conditions, making it an ideal choice for regions with insufficient precipitation [3].

The high protein content in the biomass of *Indigofera tinctoria* opens up broad prospects for its use in the livestock feed industry. Legumes have high nutritional value and can serve as an excellent source of protein for livestock. This is especially important in conditions where there is a shortage of high-quality feed for animals. In addition, the ability of *Indigofera* to recover quickly after mowing allows it to be used as a perennial crop, thereby reducing the costs of planting materials and crop maintenance [6].

The favorable climate of Uzbekistan, characterized by high solar activity and the presence of irrigated lands, creates ideal conditions for the successful cultivation of *Indigofera tinctoria*. In addition, suitable soil composition contributes to improving soil fertility and increasing yields. The integration of *Indigofera* into the region's sustainable farming systems not only improves soil composition, but also promotes the development of organic agriculture [12].

Large-scale scientific research on the cultivation, growth and development of *Indigofera tinctoria* L. in various regions of our republic, determination of its phytochemical composition, development of reproduction methods, assessment of its

introduction and development of recommendations for the organization of large-scale plantations [11].

Studies conducted on the cultivation of *Indigofera tinctoria* L. allow to establish the optimal conditions for its successful development. This plant prefers sunny places with well-drained soils. This allows to optimize the cultivation processes and ensure high yields [2].

Analysis of the phytochemical composition of *Indigofera tinctoria* L. is an important stage of research, as it allows to identify the presence valuable biologically active substances. Studying the composition of the plant may reveal the presence of natural dyes that can be used in the textile industry [8,9].

The development of reproduction methods for *Indigofera tinctoria* L. plays a key role in ensuring its population sustainability. Cultivating the plant from seeds or cuttings can expand its range and preserve genetic diversity [14].

CONCLUSION. Evaluating the introduction of *Indigofera tinctoria* L. to various regions helps determine how successfully the plant adapts to new conditions. When introduced to arid regions, it may be found that the plant requires additional watering for normal development [13].

Developing recommendations for organizing large-scale plantations of *Indigofera tinctoria* L. involves analyzing economic feasibility, determining optimal planting density, and developing fertilization methods. Studies may show that growing this plant on large areas is economically justified due to the high price of the product.

REFERENCES

1. Абдиев А.А. Тугунак бактериялар – биологик азот манбаи // Ўзбекистон жанубида фермерликни ривожлантириш муаммолари. Республика илмий-амалий конф. маърузалар тўплами. – Қарши, 2006. – Б. 40.
2. Абдурахмонова У., Мухаммадиев Ш.Ж. *Indigofera tinctoria* L. ўсимлиги илдизининг кимёвий таркибини ўрганиш // Science and Scientific Journal, 2021. – Б. 63-67.
3. Гулиев В. Ш., Мирзалиев Д. Д., Гумбатов Г. С. Рекомендации по выращиванию и использованию басмы в Азербайджане. Аннотированный перечень законченных научно-исследовательских работ, рекомендованных к внедрению в сельскохозяйственное производство. – Гянджа, 1993. – С. 36-37.
4. Джумаев Ф.Х., Атаева З.А. Выращивание растения *Indigofera tinctoria* L. и его роль в повышении плодородия почв в условиях Бухарской области // Вестник науки и образования. – 2021. – № 3-2 (106). – С. 6-8.

5. Ёкубов Г., Эргашев А., Рахимов А., Эшчанов Р. О режиме минерального питания растения *Indigofera tinctoria* // Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалиги. – Тошкент, 2009. – № 12. – Б. 19.
6. Ёкубов Ғ.Қ. Индигофера ўсимлигини етиштиришда кўчат қалинлигини биомасса ҳосилдорлигига таъсири // Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалиги. – Тошкент, 2010. – № 12. – Б. 23.
7. Ёкубов Ғ.Қ., Рахимов А., Эшчанов Р., Эргашев А. *Indigofera tinctoria* ўсимлигининг такрорий экин сифатида ҳосилдорлик ва тупроқ унумдорлигига таъсири // Ўзбекистон Республикаси Фанлар академияси маърузалари. – Тошкент, 2011. – № 1. – Б. 84-86.
8. Ихласова Б.И. Крашение растительными красителями с точки зрения химии. // Проджи. – № 9. – 2009. – С. 6-27.
9. Касумов М.А. Флористический анализ красильных растений Азербайджана // Докл. АН Азербайджана. – 1995. – Т. 51–52. – С. 1–12, С. 129–140.
10. Маткаримова А.А., Болтабаева А.С., Турабоева Г.Н., Қиличева М.Г. *Indigofera L.* ўсимлиги уруғларининг ЎЗМУ Ботаника боғи шароитида ўсиши ва ривожланиш хусусиятлари // Илм-фан тараққиётида замонавий методларнинг қўлланилиши: Республика илмий-амалий онлайн конференцияси. – Тошкент, 2020. – Б. 95-99.
11. Мирзаахмедов Р. Табиий ранглар технологияси. – ЮНЕСКО, 2007. – 80 б.
12. Рахимов А. ва бошқалар. Нил бўёғи ўсимлигини етиштириш, табиий бўёқ биотехнологияси ҳамда емирилган ерларни яхшилаш // Фермерлар учун ўқув-услубий қўлланма. – Тошкент: Бактрия Пресс, 2012. – 32 б.
13. Флора Ўзбекистана. – Тошкент, 1941-1962. – 301 б.
14. Шишкин Б.К. Род Индигофера – *Indigofera L.* // Флора СССР: в 30 т. / гл. ред. В.Л. Комаров. – М.-Л.: Изд-во АН СССР, 1945. – С. 298-300.